

Project¹ Number: 660067

Project Acronym: COLD μ WAVE

Project title: Energy Innovative Food Process For The Production Of High Quality Frozen Food

Modelling and computer simulations of microwave blanching of fruits

¹ The term 'project' used in this template equates to an 'action' in certain other Horizon 2020 documentation

According to the DoA of COLDμWAVE proposal, during the implementation of Work Package 1, a report regarding the computer simulation of blanching will be delivered.

The computational modelling for the Microwave blanching of fruits was based on the prototype Microwave equipment that was designed, constructed and described in deliverable 1.1. The cavity that the blanching was modelled and validated had the dimensions of 29.5 cm x 31.5 cm x 20 cm (width x depth x height) (Figure 1).

Figure 1.

The model was solved using the finite element method (FEM) in Comsol Multiphysics 4.2.

Electromagnetic field simulation

$$\text{Maxwell equation: } \nabla \times \mu_r^{-1}(\nabla \times \vec{E}) - k_0^{-1} \left(\epsilon_r - \frac{j\sigma}{\omega\epsilon_0} \right) \vec{E} = 0$$

μ_r^{-1} : relative permeability of the material

\vec{E} : Electric field vector $\mathbf{E}=[E_x, E_y, E_z]$

k_0^{-1} : Wave number of free space - $k_0 = \omega\sqrt{\epsilon_0\mu_0} = \frac{\omega}{c_0} = \frac{2\pi f}{c_0}$ (related to frequency)

ϵ_r : dielectric constant (ϵ')

ϵ_0 : vacuum permittivity

σ : electrical conductivity

$\frac{\sigma}{\omega\epsilon_0}$: equal to ϵ''

Temperature distribution simulation

$$\rho c_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + \rho c_p \vec{u}_{trans} \nabla T = \nabla \cdot (k \nabla T) + Q$$

ρ : total density of the sample

c_p : heat capacity of the sample

u_{trans} : convective velocity (for sample holder is 0, for mango is the intrinsic velocity of water flow)

$$\vec{u}_{trans} = -\frac{k_L}{\mu_L} \nabla P$$

μ_L : viscosity of water

$$k_L = k_i \cdot S_g$$

S_g : gas saturation (volume fraction of the pores that are filled with gas)

$$S_g = 1 - S_w$$

$$k_i = \frac{k \cdot \varepsilon^3}{(1 - \varepsilon)^2}$$

k_i : intrinsic permeability

k : permeability constant

∇T : derivative of Temperature in space

k : thermal conductivity

Q : thermal source

$$Q = Q_{MW} + Q_{evap/cond}$$

$$Q_{MW} = \frac{1}{2} \pi f \varepsilon'' \varepsilon_0 |E|^2 : MW \text{ dissipated heat}$$

$$Q_{evap/cond} = \frac{-\Delta H_{evap} \cdot c_{evap} M_w (P_{eq} - P_v)}{RT} : \text{heat of evaporation/condensation}$$

ΔH_{evap} : enthalpy of evaporation

c_{evap} : evaporation constant

M_w : molar mass of water

$$a_w = f(T, M)$$

$$M = \frac{\rho_{\text{liquid water}} \cdot S_w \cdot \varepsilon}{\rho_{\text{solid matrix}} (1 - \varepsilon)} : \text{moisture content}$$

S_w : water saturation

ε : porosity of the matrix

P_{eq} : Pressure of equilibrium

$$P_{eq} = P_{w_sat} \cdot a_w$$

P_v : vapor pressure

$$P_v = P \cdot X_v :$$

P : total pressure

X_v : molar ratio of vapor into gas phase

Liquid Water – mass balance

$$\varepsilon \frac{dS_w}{dt} + \nabla \cdot (-\varepsilon D \nabla S_w + \vec{u}_{trans} \varepsilon S_w) = \frac{-S_{evap/cond}}{\rho_w}$$

$$S_{evap/cond} = \frac{c_{evap} \cdot M_w (P_{eq} - P_v)}{RT}$$

$$\vec{u}_{trans} = -\frac{k_L}{\mu_L} \nabla P$$

Gas Phase overall mass balance

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\rho \varepsilon_p) + \nabla (\rho \vec{u}_g) = Q_m$$

$$\rho = \frac{P M_{mean}}{RT} \text{ density of whole gas given according to ideal gas}$$

$$\varepsilon_p = \varepsilon \cdot S_g$$

$$Q_m = S_{evap/cond}$$

$$\vec{u}_g = -\frac{k_g}{\mu_g} \nabla P \text{ convective velocity of gas phase}$$

$$k_g = k_i \cdot S_g, k_i: \text{intrinsic permeability}$$

Water Vapor mass balance

$$\rho \frac{\partial w_v}{\partial t} + \nabla (\rho D_{v/air} \nabla w_v) + \rho (\vec{u}_g \cdot \nabla) w_v = (1 - w_v) S_{evap/cond}$$

w_v : water/vapor weight fraction

$D_{v/air}$: diffusion coefficient of water vapor in air

SIMULATIONS

Electromagnetic field simulation

Temperature distribution

The liquid volume fraction of water in the porous space during the heating

The evolution of the total gas phase mass inside mango during the heating

The evolution of the water vapor/air composition of the gas phase

